

ANALYSIS OF AGRICULTURE ONE OF THE LEADING SECTORS IN THE MODERNIZATION OF THE NATIONAL ECONOMY

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***Аннотация:** Ушбу мақолада миллий иқтисодиётни модернизациялаш шароитида етакчи тармоқлардан бири сифатида қишлоқ хўжалиги соҳасини таҳлиliga доир илмий тадқиқот ишлари ва ушбу соҳани ривожлантириш бўйича бир неча таклифлар келтиб ўтилган.*

***Калит сўзлар:** иқтисодиёт, интеграция, саноат, аграр соҳа, самарадорлик, ислоҳот.*

***Аннотация:** В данной статье представлены научно-исследовательские работы по анализу аграрного сектора как ведущей отрасли в условиях модернизации национальной экономики и несколько предложений по развитию этого сектора.*

***Ключевые слова:** экономика, интеграция, промышленность, аграрный сектор, эффективность, реформа.*

***Annotation:** This article presents research work on the analysis of the agricultural sector as a leading industry in the context of the modernization of the national economy and several proposals for the development of this sector.*

***Key words:** economy, integration, industry, agricultural sector, efficiency, reform.*

In the development strategy of New Uzbekistan for 2022-2026, "Intensive development of agriculture on a scientific basis, increasing soil fertility, improving the system of providing agro-services based on science and innovation, increasing the production volume of agro-industrial enterprises by 1.5 times, developing agro-

logistic centers, modern laboratories tasks such as increasing the number, implementing a national program on seed and seedling production, establishing an international agricultural university, and deepening the integration of science and practice in the field" [1]. Currently, one of the urgent tasks is to eliminate the factors that have a negative impact on the sustainable development of farmers and farms, to further strengthen the support of the farming movement by the state, to create conditions aimed at ensuring that it becomes a leading force in society, and to increase the income of farmers and farmers by diversifying production. It is important to find optimal solutions to problems aimed at increasing. At the same time, a complex statistical analysis of agricultural production processes in our republic, a multi-factor assessment of economic development trends of farms, development of scientific proposals and practical recommendations on problems in the development of the agricultural sector in the region and their solutions is an urgent and important issue.

Many local and foreign scientists and specialists have conducted extensive scientific research on increasing the efficiency of agricultural production and statistical evaluation of its structural structures. In particular, Kh. D. Khojakulov., N. Kh. Rashitova., N. N. Askarov., S. N. Sayfullaev [2] the methodological aspects of the statistical analysis of structural changes in the agrarian sector, T. Shodiev [3] the economic analysis of the agricultural network while they scientifically researched the theoretical and practical aspects of econometric models of development, B. Berkinov, K. A. Choriev, [4] liberalized agriculture in our country, formed the optimal structure of arable land, structural and economic mechanisms of farming, models of agro-industrial complex, agriculture the issues of effective organization of the economy, V.L. Somov [5], who promoted scientific research on the analysis of economic development and efficiency of agriculture using statistical methods. In particular, in the scientific article "Statistical analysis of production processes in the agrarian sector by forms of economic management"

by professor Kh. Khojakulov, the specific characteristics of agricultural production in our country, the role of economic entities in them, the level and dynamics of production by economic categories are statistically evaluated. scientific conclusions were drawn. The table below shows the main indicators of the agriculture of our republic. Table 1.

Table 1.

Main indicators of agriculture

Sown area of agricultural crops, thousand hectares	2014	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019	2020	2021
Agricultural products, billion soums	3678,2	3694,2	3706,7	3474,5	3396	3309,4	3396,1	3260,7
Agricultural products, bln. soum	81794,3	99604,6	115599,2	148199,3	187425,6	216283,1	250250,6	303415,5
farming	43194,3	55429,2	61755,1	83303,4	98406,4	111904,8	123858,8	152130,4
animal husbandry	38600	44175,4	53844,1	64895,9	89019,2	104378,3	126391,8	151285,1

In the scientific article "Economic-statistical analysis of the production of agricultural products" by Q.K. Jumaev, the current situation of the production of agricultural products in our country, the role of the industry in the economy of the country, the economic analysis of their main areas of economic activities, and the main problems that need to be implemented in the development of the industry and directions are outlined. B. Utanov's scientific article on the topic "Integral indicators representing the efficiency of multi-sectoral farms" describes the activity of multi-sectoral farms in our republic and their economic determination and integrated indicators system is scientifically based. Q. Berdigulov's scientific article entitled "Statistical analysis of structural changes in agriculture" describes the regulatory documents adopted in the following year on the further development

of agriculture and the processes of its implementation, the problems in the methodology implemented in agriculture and ways to eliminate them.

T.G. In the scientific article "Labor productivity as a factor of sustainable development of agricultural enterprises" by Kolesnikova and others, the role of the labor factor in the economic development of the agrarian sector, its characteristics, economic-statistical analysis of the level and dynamics of labor productivity in agricultural enterprises are highlighted. In the above studies, the development and structural changes of the agricultural network were analyzed using statistical methods at various levels, theoretically and methodologically studied, but in the current conditions, the agricultural network of our country is analyzed in depth and the main directions of the development of the network, structural changes, based on the identification of trends in it, are sufficiently researched. not implemented. In the successful formation and development of farms in Uzbekistan, it is necessary to raise the development of the cooperative movement in the countryside to such a level that it should cover not only production, but also product processing and sale.

It is worth noting that the transition of agricultural management to the most efficient farming movement, which has fully justified itself in the experience of developed countries, started a new era in the development of the sector. As a result of the introduction of the farming movement, people's attitude towards the land changed, they developed a sense of ownership. This made it possible not only to increase the quality and volume of the produced products, but also to increase people's interest in their work and their well-being. At the same time, farmers, who are well aware of their rights and obligations, have become the leading force implementing reforms in the countryside.

Based on the above information, we offer the following in order to further develop and improve the efficiency of the agricultural sector in our republic:

- In the current conditions, improving the statistical methodology of the agricultural network is an important issue. For this purpose, the following main

tasks are recommended: development of a program for conducting statistical monitoring of network activities (total, sample, questionnaire, monographic observations, etc.);

- improvement of the system of indicators describing the financial results of agricultural activity (productivity, product cost, profit);

- statistical analysis of the absolute and relative changes in the volume of production of the main types of agricultural products (farming and animal husbandry); analysis of structural changes in the scale of production of the main types of agricultural products;

- Carrying out regional comparisons of the main indicators of the scale of agricultural production in our country using various statistical methods (economic indices, correlation-regression analysis, etc.);

- Statistical modeling of time series describing the results of production of agricultural products and development of medium-term forecasts; Comprehensive statistical analysis of various factors affecting the results of agricultural production activities and development of scientific and practical proposals based on them.

Today, the development of multi-sectoral farms has become an important aspect of the country's development, especially the main force in ensuring the permanent employment and well-being of the rural population, and is one of the important factors in the development of the country's economy. In the future, it is necessary to solve the main problems faced by multi-sector farms, to develop necessary measures for their full state support.

List of references

1. Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated January 28, 2022 No. PF-60 on the development strategy of New Uzbekistan for 2022-2026. (<https://lex.uz/>).

2. Khojakulov Kh.D., Rashitova N.Kh., Askarov N.N., Sayfullaev S.N. Development of effective ways of structural changes in the context of

modernization and diversification of the economy based on statistical methods.

Monograph. - T.: ECONOMY-FINANCE, 2018. - 206 p.

3. Shadiev T.Sh. Economic models of agricultural development. - T.: Science, 1986. - 168 p.

4. Choriev K.A., Berkinov B. Legal and regulatory basis of organization and management of farmers and farms. - T.: Sharq. 2002. - 16 b.

5. Somov V.L. Economic and statistical analysis of the development of agriculture in the Saratov region // Questions of statistics, 2019, T.26, No. 6. – S. 47-54.

Xulkarbonu, Y. (2017). THE ROLE AND PLACE OF ECOTOURISM IN THE REGIONAL ECONOMY OF THE REPUBLIC OF UZBEKISTAN. *Экономика и социум*, (4 (35)), 15-18.

Egamberdiyev, F. T., & Yoqubjonova, X. (2017). FEATURES OF ECOTOURISM DEVELOPMENT. *Экономика и социум*, (4 (35)), 19-21.

Yakubjonova, H. (2020). SOCIO-ECONOMIC COMMUNICATION BETWEEN ECOTOURISM AND NATURE. In *НАУКА И ТЕХНИКА. МИРОВЫЕ ИССЛЕДОВАНИЯ* (pp. 11-13).

Yakubjanova, H. Y. (2018). Environmental ecotourism in Uzbekistan innovative way. *Теория и практика современной науки*, (3), 108-110.

Якубжанова, Х. Я. (2019). Анализ зарубежного опыта в развитии экотуризма: на примере Ферганского экономического района. *Региональная экономика: теория и практика*, 17(8), 1593-1606.

Yokubovna, Y. H. (2019). Evaluation of the economic impact of local population in the development of regional economy: an example of Chadak village. *American Journal of Economics and Business Management*, 2(3), 83-93.

Yoqubjonova, H. Y. (2019). Ecotourism in the economy of the regions. *Форум молодых ученых*, (3 (31)), 57-61.